

K-Means Clustering for Color-Based Product Recommendation in Interior Design

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Abstract— Product recommendation based on color analysis and classification using machine learning techniques. This takes an image as input, applies KMeans clustering to identify dominant colors, and returns a list of products from a database that match those colors. The resulting products can be used for recommending items to customers based on their color preferences. This can be applied to an online interior design website, where customers can upload an image and receive recommendations for products that match the colors in the image. This can be applied to various industries, including interior design. By incorporating this feature in an interior design website, customers can receive personalized recommendations for products that match the colors in their room, making the interior design process more efficient and enjoyable.

Keywords—Recommendation, Color analysis, RGB, KMeans clustering, Machine learning, OpenCV, NumPy

I. INTRODUCTION

Color analysis and classification is a powerful technique used in various fields such as image processing, machine learning, and interior design to identify and analyze the dominant colors in an image. In interior design, analyzing color is crucial for creating a cohesive and aesthetically pleasing look in a room. This technique involves clustering the pixels of an image into groups based on their color similarity and identifying the most frequent or representative colors in each group. In the context of an interior design website, color analysis and classification can be used to recommend products to customers based on their color preferences. By analyzing the colors in an image that a customer uploads or selects, a system can identify the dominant colors and recommend products that match or complement those colors. This can help improve the overall customer experience and increase sales for the website. The process involves uploading an image to the website, identifying the dominant colors using K-means clustering, and recommending products from a database that match those colors.

Overall, the color analysis function provides a valuable tool for an interior design website to recommend products that match the color preferences of their customers, potentially improving sales and customer satisfaction. By incorporating this feature into the website, customers can receive personalized recommendations for products that fit the color scheme of their room, making the interior design process more efficient and enjoyable.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Patil Siddhant Vitthal, Sundaresan Balasubramanian, Pravin S. Mane [1], proposes the “Color Analysis and Classification Based on Machine Learning Technique Using RGB Camera” they discuss the development of an automated system for color matching in the fabric industry to increase accuracy, precision, and production rates. The system uses software that can be run on a normal PC and an Allied vision GigE camera for image acquisition. The OpenCV library and Python 3.6.1 are used for accessing Image Processing tools, and a user-friendly GUI has been developed on the C#.NET Framework 4.5. The paper also compares different background removal techniques and explains the Euclidian distance method and the k-means color clustering method for image post-processing to sort the fabric. Two methods, namely the ‘Euclidian distance method’ and ‘k- means color clustering method’ for color matching have been compared. This comparison is done for the classification. Overall, the system has the potential to reduce manufacturing costs by avoiding the use of special hardware for a specific task and the subjectivity introduced by human inspection..

S. Prasanna, N. Priyadarshini and M. Arul Pugazhendhi [2], proposes the “Textile Robot for Matching and Pick Up Clothes Based on Color Recognition”, this is based on a system designed to assist in the process of sorting and organizing clothes based on color. Color detection is by open CV library, first image captured color is processed as Changing Color-space There are more than 150 color-space conversion methods available in OpenCV. The system uses color recognition technology through the OpenCV library to identify the color of each piece of clothing. The first step in the process is capturing an image of the clothing item. The image is then processed through the OpenCV library by changing the color space from BGR to HSV. The HSV image is then thresholded to isolate the specific color range of the clothing item, allowing for extraction of the color alone. This system offers an efficient and accurate way to sort and organize clothing items based on color, reducing the time and effort required to complete the task manually.

Tanvi Gupta and Supriya P Panda[3], proposes the “Clustering Validation of CLARA and k-means Using Silhouette & DUNN Measures on Iris Dataset”, this is based on the comparison of two clustering techniques, CLARA and K-Means, using the popular Iris dataset. The paper examines various cluster validation measures, including cluster plot, Silhouette plot, and Dunn Index, to evaluate the performance of each clustering technique. The statistical

analysis was performed using the R programming language. The results show that CLARA clustering outperforms K-Means clustering based on the cluster validation measures. Overall, the paper highlights the importance of selecting the appropriate clustering technique and validation measures for effective data analysis.

Ni Made Satvika Iswari, Wella and Andre Rusli[4], proposes the “Product Recommendation for e-Commerce System Based on Ontology”, the development of a product recommendation system for e-commerce platforms using the Slope One algorithm based on domain ontology. The aim of the study is to help users find products that suit their needs and to assist sellers in increasing their sales. Collaborative Filtering is used to produce recommendations, and the Slope One algorithm is applied to the input rating based on the domain ontology of the product to represent relationships between products. The recommendation system is expected to provide more varied recommendations that are in line with user interests, including recommendations for specific products and categories of interest. The study concludes that the ontology approach can improve the accuracy of product recommendations and provide a better user experience.

Jelili Oyelade, Itunuoluwa Isewon, Obembe Olowole, “Data Clustering: Algorithms and Its Applications”, this discusses the importance of clustering and classification in analyzing data in various fields like machine learning, bioinformatics, statistics, and pattern recognition. Different clustering methods like partitioning, hierarchical, density-based, grid-based, soft clustering, model-based, and ensemble clustering are explained. The challenges and problems associated with clustering, such as misinterpretation of results, efficiency, and performance of clustering algorithms, are discussed.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The initial interaction of the system with the user. A user sends an HTTP POST request to the web server with an image file and a category ID. The image file is the input image that the user wants to analyze, and the category ID refers to the category of products that the user is interested in. The system receives this request and retrieves the image and category ID from the request object. The system then proceeds to the next step, which is image preprocessing.

After receiving the image file in the HTTP request, the next step in the color analysis process is to read and preprocess the image file using OpenCV and NumPy. OpenCV (Open-Source Computer Vision) is a popular library of programming functions mainly used for real-time computer vision applications. In this process, OpenCV is used to read the image file and convert it from the BGR color space (default in OpenCV) to the RGB color space. The image is then passed through NumPy to prepare it for analysis. NumPy is a library for the Python programming language that provides support for large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, along with a large collection of mathematical functions to operate on these arrays. In this process, NumPy is used to preprocess the image file to prepare it for analysis. The preprocessing step involves resizing the image to a standard size (in this case, 900x600 pixels) and flattening it into a one-dimensional array. This is done to simplify the color analysis process by reducing the number of pixels to be analyzed. Overall, the purpose of this

step is to convert the image into a format that can be processed and analyzed by the color analysis algorithm.

The K-Means clustering algorithm is a commonly used unsupervised machine learning algorithm that is used for clustering data points into groups based on their similarity. In the context of color analysis, the K-Means algorithm is used to identify the dominant colors in an image. Once the preprocessed image is obtained, the K-Means algorithm is applied to the image data. The K-Means algorithm works by first randomly initializing a set of cluster centroids, and then iteratively updating the centroids to minimize the distance between the data points and the centroids. The number of clusters (i.e., dominant colors) to be identified is typically specified by the user. In this code, the K-Means algorithm is applied to the preprocessed image using the ‘sklearn.cluster.KMeans’ class. The number of clusters is set to 2, and the ‘fit_predict ()’ method is used to fit the data to the model and obtain the predicted cluster labels for each data point. The cluster centers (i.e., the dominant colors) are then obtained using the ‘cluster_centers_’ attribute of the KMeans object.

After applying the K-Means clustering algorithm to identify the dominant colors in the image, we obtain the RGB values of those colors. However, in order to use these colors to filter the relevant products in the database, we need to convert these RGB values into their corresponding hexadecimal values. The conversion is done using a function called `rgb_hex(color)` that takes an RGB value as input and returns the corresponding hexadecimal value. The function first converts the RGB values to integers using the `int ()` function and then formats the resulting integers as hexadecimal values using the `format ()` function. The resulting hexadecimal value is then returned as a string with the “#” symbol added to the beginning, which is the standard way of representing hexadecimal colors in HTML and CSS. Once we have the hexadecimal values of the dominant colors, we can use them to filter the relevant products in the database.

Once the dominant colors of the uploaded image are identified, the code uses the category ID provided in the HTTP request to filter products in the database that belong to that category. This is done using the filter method of the Django ORM (Object-Relational Mapping) to retrieve all products from the database that match the given category ID.

```
category_id = request.POST.get('category_id')
```

```
products = Product.objects.
```

```
filter(category_id=category_id).filter(*color_filters)
```

Here, the `category_id` is retrieved from the HTTP POST request, and the filter method is used to get all the products that belong to this category. The `color_filters` list is then passed to the filter method using the unpacking operator `*`, which filters the products based on their colors. This list contains `Q` objects that define the color filters based on the hexadecimal values of the dominant colors. Finally, the filtered products are returned as a context variable to the `color_analysis.html` template, which renders the recommended products to the user.

After identifying the dominant colors in the uploaded image, the system will create a list of hex codes for the colors using the RGB to hexadecimal conversion function.

These hex codes are then used to filter the products stored in the database, ensuring that only products that match the dominant colors in the uploaded image are recommended. This is done by first creating a filter for each dominant color. Then, these filters are applied to the list of products in the database using the filter () method. This will result in a list of products that contain at least one of the dominant colors in their color field. The final list of recommended products is then passed to the render () function along with the HTTP request. This function generates the HTML page that displays the recommended products to the user.

After filtering the products based on their colors that match the dominant colors in the input image, the final step is to return these filtered products to the user interface for display. This is achieved by rendering an HTML template using the Django's render () function.

The render () function takes three arguments: the request object, the name of the HTML template, and a dictionary containing the context variables to be passed to the template. In this case, the filtered products are passed to the template as a context variable, which can be accessed and displayed in the HTML template. The HTML template contains the necessary code to display the filtered products to the user. This typically involves iterating through the list of products and displaying their details, such as name, description, image, price, etc. The exact layout and design of the HTML template depends on the requirements of the application and the preferences of the developer.

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IV. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

```
def rgb_hex(color):  
hex_color = "#{:02x} {:02x} {:02x}".format(int(color[0]),  
int(color[1]), int(color[2]))  
return hex_color
```

The rgb_hex () function takes a tuple color of three integer values representing an RGB color, and returns the corresponding hexadecimal color code as a string. The function works by first using the format () method to format the hexadecimal representation of the color as #{RRGGBB}, where RR, GG, and BB are the two-digit hexadecimal representations of the red, green, and blue components of the color, respectively. The :02x format specifier ensures that each component is represented by two digits, with leading zeros if necessary. Next, the int() function is used to convert each component of the color tuple to an integer value, since the format() method requires integer values. Finally, the resulting string hex_color is returned as the output of the function.

```
def prep_image(raw_img):  
modified_img = cv.resize(raw_img,(900,  
600),interpolation=cv.INTER_AREA)  
modified_img = modified_img.  
reshape(modified_img.shape[0]*modified_img.shape[1],  
3) return modified_img
```

The prep_image () function takes a raw image raw_img as input, and resizes it to a fixed size of (900, 600) using cv.resize(), and then reshapes it into a two-dimensional NumPy array of shape (N, 3) where N is the total number of pixels in the image and 3 represents the three color channels (red, green, and blue). The cv. resize () function resizes the input image to the fixed size of (900, 600) using the interpolation=cv.INTER_AREA parameter, which specifies that the area-based resampling algorithm should be used for down sampling the image. This reduces the size of the image while preserving its aspect ratio. The reshape () method is then used to reshape the 3D NumPy array returned by cv.resize() into a 2D NumPy array of shape (N, 3), where N is the total number of pixels in the image. This is done by multiplying the number of rows and columns of the 3D array using the shape attribute, and then reshaping the array into a new shape of (N, 3). The resulting NumPy array modified_img is then returned as the output of the function. Overall, the purpose of this function is to prepare the input image for color analysis by reshaping it into a 2D array of RGB pixel values.

```
def color_analysis(request):  
if request.method == 'POST': image  
= request.FILES['image']  
img = cv.imdecode(np.fromstring(image.read(), np.uint8),  
cv.IMREAD_UNCHANGED)  
img = cv.cvtColor(img,  
cv.COLOR_BGR2RGB) modified_img =  
prep_image(img)
```

This code defines a view function called color_analysis that takes a request object as an argument. Inside the function, it first checks if the request method is POST using the if statement. If the request method is POST, it gets the uploaded image from the request object using request. FILES['image'], which assumes that the image is uploaded using a form with an input field named "image". Then it decodes the image using cv.imdecode from the OpenCV library, which converts the image from a byte string to a NumPy array. The np.fromstring function converts the byte string to a NumPy array, and cv.IMREAD_UNCHANGED flag reads the image as it is, including the alpha channel if it exists. It then converts the image from the default BGR color space to the RGB color space using cv.cvtColor. Finally, it prepares the image for color analysis by resizing it to 900x600 pixels using cv.resize and reshaping it into a 2D array with three columns (R, G, B) using prep_image.

```
clf = KMeans(n_clusters=2, n_init=10) color_labels =  
clf.fit_predict(modified_img) center_colors  
= clf.cluster_centers_
```

This code performs K-means clustering on the image pixels to determine the dominant colors in the image. The KMeans

we want to identify two dominant colors in the image. The `fit_predict` method of the `clf` object is called on the modified `_img` array to predict the cluster labels for each pixel. The `cluster_centers_` attribute of the `clf` object is used to get the RGB values of the cluster centers, which represent the dominant colors.

```
counts = Counter(color_labels)
```

```
ordered_colors = [center_colors[i] for i in counts.keys()]
```

```
hex_colors = [rgb_hex(ordered_colors[i]) for i in
```

```
counts.keys()]
```

After applying K-means clustering, the code uses the `Counter` function to count the number of pixels in each cluster. The `color_labels` array obtained from `fit_predict` function represents the cluster labels for each pixel in the image. The `counts` variable stores the frequency of each label. The `keys()` method is called on the `counts` object to get the unique cluster labels. The `ordered_colors` list is created by iterating through the unique cluster labels and selecting the corresponding color from the `center_colors` array, which contains the RGB values of the cluster centers. This ensures that the colors in `ordered_colors` are in the same order as the labels in `counts`. Finally, the `hex_colors` list is created by iterating through the unique cluster labels and converting the corresponding color from `ordered_colors` to its hex code using the `rgb_hex` function. The `hex_colors` list represents the dominant colors in the image.

```
category_id = request.POST.get('category_id') color_filters = [Q(color__contains=color) for color in hex_colors]
```

```
products =
```

```
Product.objects.filter(category_id=category_id).filter(*color_filters)
```

```
return render(request, 'color_analysis.html', {'products': products})
```

In this code block, the function retrieves the category ID selected by the user in the POST request. Then, it creates a list of color filters based on the dominant colors in the uploaded image. Each filter is a Django Q object that queries for products whose color field contains the corresponding hex code. Finally, the function queries the Product model in the

database for products that match the category ID and any of the color filters. The resulting products are passed to the `color_analysis.html` template for display. Overall, this code block performs the main functionality of the color analysis web application, which is to retrieve and display products that match the dominant colors in a user-uploaded image.

```
categories = Category.objects.all()
```

```
return render(request, 'upload_image.html', {'categories': categories})
```

This code retrieves all instances of the Category model using the `all()` method and assigns them to the `categories` variable.

Then it renders the `upload_image.html` template with the `categories` variable passed as context. The template will use the `categories` variable to populate a dropdown list of available categories for the user to choose from.

V. RESULT

Once the form is submitted, the image is processed using the OpenCV and scikit-learn libraries to perform color clustering on the image pixels.

The `prep_image()` function resizes the image to a fixed size and flattens it into a 2D array of RGB values. The KMeans algorithm is then used to cluster the colors into two groups, and the dominant colors are identified using a Counter object and extracted as hexadecimal values. The product database is queried using the extracted colors and the selected category using the `Product.objects.filter()` method. The results are displayed in the `color_analysis.html` template, which lists the products that match the dominant colors in the image.

VI. CONCLUSION

In the context of an interior design website, product recommendation based on color analysis and classification can help customers find decor items that match the color palette of their room. By analyzing the dominant colors in an uploaded image of the room, the system can recommend furniture, curtains, or decor items that complement those colors. This can provide a personalized shopping experience for customers and can potentially increase sales and customer satisfaction. Overall, color analysis and classification using machine learning techniques have the potential to revolutionize the way we decorate our homes and improve the overall shopping experience in the interior design industry.

VII. REFERENCES

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